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Mapping Current Curricular Changes in European Engineering Education

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ABSTRACT

In Europe, there is a wide variety of curriculum designs in higher engineering education. Several international networks serve the goal of supporting the inherent need of higher education institutions to continuously improve their programmes, without per se offering a formal accreditation standard. In this paper, two such networks are considered: CDIO and SEFI. The curricular landscape across Europe and across the different engineering disciplines is mapped by means of a survey amongst the members of CDIO and SEFI. The results amongst 82 respondents show that the prevailing curriculum structure defined by focus, set-up and design is a fixed curriculum with flexible elements, focused on theory with skills woven in, and with a subject-centred curriculum, followed by another big group having a flexible curriculum with fixed elements, competency-based, and focusing on skills with theory woven in. Configurations vary based on region, engineering discipline and network membership.

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Curricular changes in the past three years and coming two years focus mostly on assessment and examination, as well as pedagogics, interpersonal skills and curriculum flexibility. Certain engineering disciplines are more prone to curriculum change than others, such as Design Engineering and Information Engineering. Electric engineering currently shows significantly less curriculum change. When changing the curriculum design, learning goals, learning activities and learning vision are typically seen as a priority in engineering education. The most perceived barriers in the curriculum change process are staff competency and engagement for those about to make changes, and development time and costs for those having made recent changes.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Mapping the state of the art in higher engineering education curriculum improvement

In Europe higher education institutions continuously work on improving the quality of their education in general and the curriculum designs of their programmes in particular, and engineering education is no exception to this. Content, didactics and organizational aspects of engineering education curricula are periodically evaluated and improved according to a set of quality criteria, determined on both national and international bases. Some are required by European laws and agreements or the national accreditation system, others are part of the institution's core policies or a strategic choice of a department or faculty itself. Currently, there is a wide variety of curriculum designs and innovations in European engineering education.

New educational science research insights seep into the aims of curriculum design improvements and its quality enhancement criteria. When looking at the proceedings of the international engineering education network conferences, certain trends can be seen, fed by both fundamental and more practice based educational research. For instance, 21st century skills have been extensively researched, initially resulting in many models of what these skills exactly are, extending to what pivotal elements a curriculum of the 21st century would need: cross-curricular key skills, learning through experience, learning outside the direct academic context, blended learning etc. (Mishra and Kereluik, 2011). An example of this is the role that reflection and critical thinking skills should play in engineering education, which has been acknowledged and redefined in the past decade (Buch and Bucciarelli, 2015). Kirschner et. al. (2006) found evidence for a higher effectiveness in learning by using guided, just-in-time instruction, in order to deal properly with expert-novice differences and critical cognitive load in students. This is the basis for curriculum models such as 4C/ID (Merriënboer et. al., 2002), and supports the emphasis on integration within a curriculum of offered knowledge and skills in authentic, complex projects within CDIO (Crawley et. al., 2011). Another trend that influences curriculum design is the role higher education institutions can play in open innovation networks (Hallenga-Brink and Vervoort, 2015), between education, research and the professional practice. From an educational point of view, this way students work with the work field during their studies, challenged to address topics such as sustainability, ethics, cultural differences and international communication. Another growing trend is the flexible curriculum, aimed to be better fit the entry level and individual learning preferences of students, the multidisciplinary nature of the near-future work field, and the speed with which society's needs and technological possibilities are developing (Sinke et. al., 2015).

Applying these research insights in engineering education has impact on the structure and design of the curriculum, and prompts alterations on one or more of the curriculum design axes as described by van den Akker et. al. (2006). Currently, there is no concise overview of what curricula in engineering education in Europe typically look like, nor of the specific changes that the engineering programmes currently work on when improving their curriculum designs. This research aims to map the curricular landscape and current changes in curriculum designs across Europe in the different engineering disciplines, regions and international networks.

1.2 Barriers in higher engineering education curriculum development

It is easiest to change a curriculum when there is a high sense of urgency and a high preparedness felt within the organization (Kamp and Klaassen, 2013). When internal concerns need solving and everybody feels the need to address these concerns, involvement will not be a problem. When there is a high urgency, but low preparedness amongst the staff, leadership commitment could be an important starting point instead. And when there is a low urgency but high preparedness, capacities of staff can be explored and facilitated in a bottom-up approach. To facilitate such continuous improvement practices, Professional Learning Communities (PLC) in any form serve their purpose to equip staff with the competency to make the needed changes. According to Verbiest (2002) PLCs are built on personal capacity, the individuals' ability to (re) construct and apply knowledge in an active and reflective manner, making use of up-to-date scholarly and practical theoretical insights, on collective capacity to do this as a group, with a shared vision as starting point, and on organizational capacity, having the cultural and structural conditions to support the development. Supportive, stimulating and shared leadership is also an important aspect of this organizational capacity.

The more radical the intended changes to a curriculum are, the more barriers will be experienced by the developers within the structure of their higher education institution, accreditation system and (inter)national laws (Hallenga-Brink, Carlsson and Georgsson, 2018). These barriers can result in delays and even cancelation of the intended curriculum developments. This research aims to map which barriers are experienced or foreseen in current engineering curriculum development in Europe, in relation to the different contextual settings of the higher education institutions (engineering discipline, region, phase of the change process).

2 METHOD

2.1 Survey amongst SEFI and CDIO members

In this research, two networks in Europe that function as international professional learning communities for engineering education are primarily considered: SEFI (Société Européenne pour la Formation des Ingénieurs) and the worldwide CDIO (Conceive – Design – Implement – Operate) which has active European and UK divisions. In 2019, SEFI has 113 institutional members, CDIO has 168 institutional members of which 69 are part of the European region. A total of 19 institutions are a member of both networks. CDIO offers a framework of guidelines plus a syllabus of learning goals to educate engineering graduates towards becoming professionals. SEFI has a thematic working groups structure and the Engineering Education Research journal. Both networks have an annual conference in which reviewed publications on educational developments are presented to share experiences and learn from each other. The proceedings of the last three years of both these SEFI and

CDIO conferences have been used as a source to list items on which to base survey questions on. An online survey has been generated and has been sent around via both networks' mailing lists, and their social media channels, to be filled in by heads of programme or other key figures within the programmes. In the survey, the code of ethics has been respected. Respondents were informed beforehand they can pull out of the survey at any moment. All respondents have indicated they give permission to anonymously process their input in the dataset.

2.2 Survey items

The survey contains several dimensions. The items have been on the SEFI and CDIO proceedings of the past three years, literature searches, and three earlier conference workshops by part of the authors on curriculum agility:

To describe what the curriculum designs of the different engineering programmes in Europe look like, their focus, set-up and structure have been specified. The main focus of a curriculum is typically either on Theory or on Skills. However, Theory Focused Curricula can have skills woven in and Skills Focused Curricula can have theory woven in, resulting in four items. The set-up of a curriculum can be described in four items: Fixed (subject supply driven), Fixed with Choice Elements (e.g. minors), Flexible with Fixed Elements (e.g. graduation project) or Flexible (student demand driven) (Georgsson, Carlsson and Hallenga-Brink, 2019). Thirdly, typifying the programme's curriculum design (Mulder and ten Cate, 2006) a distinction is made between Subject Centred, Learner Centred, Problem Centred, Challenge Centred, Project Centred, Work-Integrated Centred, and/or Competency Based curriculum designs.

Based on the conferences output, the SEFI proceedings of 2018, 2017, and 2016 and CDIO proceedings of 2018, 2017, and 2016, the following contemporary curricular changes became items in the survey: Cost effectiveness, Drop-out Rates/Non-Completion Rates, Curriculum Agility and Flexibility, Blended learning, Lifelong learning, Assessment and Examination, Graduation and Capstone Projects, Pedagogics (Active, Authentic, High-Impact etc. learning), Teacher Roles and Behaviour, Cocreation, Multi- and Interdisciplinary Learning, Talent Development of Students, Underachievement and Mediocre Student Work, Inclusiveness, Gender Equality, Cultural Diversity, Frequent Learning Disabilities (ADHD, autism, dyslexia), Personal and Interpersonal Skills of Students, Employability of Students, Internationalisation, World Citizenship, Industry Engagement, Research Engagement, Sustainability, and Ethics.

Didactic changes made to the curriculum are prioritized based on the curriculum design cobweb model as described by van den Akker et. al. (2006): Learning Vision, Learning Goals, Learning Content, Learning Activities, Learning Resources, Teacher Roles and Attitudes, Learning Groups, Learning Environment, Learning time, and Assessment.

The barriers for curriculum development were the result of workshops on flexible and agile curricula (Hallenga-Brink, Carlsson and Georgsson, 2018; Hallenga-Brink, Georgsson and Carlsson, 2019), indicated by twelve to sixteen engineering education practitioners on each occasion: Staff Skill or Competence, Staff Engagement, Student Acceptance, Senior Management Acceptance, Regulatory or Process Inertia and Blocks, Physical Infrastructure, Development Time and Costs, Operating Resources of the New Model, Passing Quality Assurance or Accreditation.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Respondents

There were 82 respondents describing distinct engineering programmes of 48 European universities to the survey. In Fig. 1 and Fig 2. the regional and engineering cluster distributions of the respondents are depicted.

Fig. 1. Regional distribution of respondents

Fig. 2. Engineering cluster distribution of the respondents

3.2 Curriculum structure

A total of 43 out of 82 programmes have a Theory Focused Curriculum with Skills woven into it. Of these 43, 72% has a Fixed Curriculum with Choice Elements, and 18% has a Flexible Curriculum with Fixed Elements. When looking at the 33% of respondents that indicate a Skills Focused Curriculum with Theory woven in, 63% has a Fixed Curriculum with Choice elements, whereas 22% has a Flexible Curriculum with Fixed elements. 12% of all respondents has a solely Theory Focused Curriculum, and only 2% a solely Skills Focused Curriculum. Fig. 3 shows the curriculum design choices for each programme set-up. The Skills with Theory programmes work mostly with Project-based, Competency-based and Learner-based designs, whereas the Theory with Skills programmes work foremost Subject-based and to a lesser extend Project-based. Fig. 4 shows the same curriculum design choices, but now split per region. The percentages are calculated in regards to the number of respondents in each region. So, 80% of all Eastern European respondents mention a Competency-based Curriculum, whereas 80% of the Southern European respondents attribute a Subject-based element to their curriculum design. Scandinavia and Western Europe show a much more even pattern, although Challenge and Problem-based does not appear to be as common in the West-European programmes.

3.3 Recent and upcoming curricular changes

About 7% of the respondents has not made any curriculum changes in the past three years, nor are planning to do so in the coming two years. 76% has done curricular changes in the past three years. In the coming two years 35% will make changes.

Fig. 3. Choices in curriculum design per type of programme set-up. The numbers in the legend correspond with the number of respondents.

Fig. 4. Curriculum design per region. Note that programmes could indicate one or more choices to describe their design.

Fig 5. shows how different clusters within engineering education choose to make different changes in their curriculum. The changes are shown on a scale 0, no changes, to 3, major changes. On average the engineering programmes' level of change over all the 21 items is 0.98, which is just below Small Changes. Electrical engineering is significantly changing their curricula less (95% confidence interval), with an average of 0.60 ± 0.11 . Design engineering programmes change most with an average of 1.20, but have a larger spread of ± 0.22 than Information Engineering, which has 1.18 ± 0.13 . The item that is most often mentioned to be worked on by the programmes is Assessment and Examination, with an average of 1.27 ± 0.38 , while Frequent Learning Disabilities yields the lowest average level of change of 0.35 over all programmes. There is one remarkable peak in the least chosen items: Design programmes work on changing the curriculum for underachievement and mediocre student results considerably more than the other disciplines. Pedagogics with an average of 1.22 ± 0.11 , has the smallest spread as all disciplines mention it frequently.

Fig. 5. Recent changes in curricula in European engineering education.

When looking at the chosen changes per region, the results are fairly homogenous per item, with the exception of Graduation and Capstone Projects, which has considerably more attention in Eastern Europe, and Assessment, which has more than average attention in the UK/Ireland. When looking at the respondents being either CDIO, SEFI or member of both networks, then CDIO-only members pay more attention to Assessment and Examination and Teaching Roles and Behaviour. Those not a member of either network pay more than average attention to Drop-out and Completion Rates. SEFI-only and combined CDIO-SEFI members remain close to the average attention paid to the different change items.

3.4 Barriers in the curriculum changing process

Fig. 6 shows a difference between the respondents that have carried out changes in the past three years and those that are planning on implementing changes in the coming two years. The largest difference can be seen in the expected barriers of Senior Management Acceptance and Regulatory or Process Inertia and Blocks. Those who have not implemented changes yet tend to expect these to be barriers, but this is not affirmed by those who have carried out changes. These differences are statistically significant at a 95% level.

In the category 'other barriers' individual respondents mentioned lack of top management support, balancing core knowledge and soft skills, the time a democratic changing process takes, scheduling conflicts and high numbers of dropout students due to industry employing them early.

Fig 6. Differences in perceived barriers depending on phase of changing.

3.5 Priorities in the curriculum design development

In Fig. 7 the differences in priorities in curriculum design can be seen split by engineering discipline. Overall, 82% of the respondents stated that Learning Goals were continuously prioritized in curriculum development. Learning Groups and Learning Time were prioritized least as opposed to Learning Activities and Learning Vision. Especially the engineering disciplines of Built Environment and Design Engineering show different paths in the plot.

Fig. 7. The different engineering disciplines show different priorities in curriculum design.

4 CONCLUSION

In Europe the majority of higher engineering education curriculum designs are either Theory focused with Skills woven in or Skills focused with Theory woven in. The curriculum set-up that goes along with this is mostly Fixed with Flexible elements and to a lesser extent Flexible with Fixed elements and completely Fixed. None of the curricula were Flexible only. There was a spread in curriculum design of combinations where Subject-based, Competency-based, and Project-Based were most often mentioned. The biggest group of subject-centred curriculum designs were mostly found in Southern Europe, Scandinavia, and the UK/Ireland. Challenge-based curriculum designs are not common in Europe.

The changes European Engineering Education programmes make currently are mostly on improving Assessment and Examination, Personal and Interpersonal Skills, Curriculum Agility and Flexibility, and Pedagogics (Active, Authentic, High Impact etc learning). Learning disabilities and Cost Effectiveness were least mentioned. Electric Engineering made or planned the least changes to their curriculum from all the engineering disciplines. Design and Information Engineering made the most, with high peaks on Student Employability, Industry Engagement, Underachievement and Mediocre Student Results, Teacher Roles and Behaviour, and Assessment and Examination. CDIO-only members paid more than average attention to the latter two items as well. Drop-out rates were mentioned most often by those respondents who were not a member of SEFI nor CDIO.

On average, barriers most mentioned as majorly influencing the development process were Staff Skills and Staff Engagement by 83% of the respondents. A difference was seen between barriers anticipated by those about to make changes and barriers experienced by those who just made changes to their curriculum. Regulatory or Process Inertia and Blocks, Management Support, Staff Competence and Engagement all proved less of a barrier for the latter group, whereas Development Time and Physical Infrastructure proved to be more of a barrier to them.

When comparing the perceived barriers by network memberships the research showed that the more involved in engineering education networks the respondents are, the less barriers they perceive. Looking at the regional differences, the Scandinavian engineering programmes indicate less barriers overall than any of the other regions.

This research describes the vast map of curricular structures and changes made in engineering education curriculums in Europe. The results describe differences between geographical regions and clusters of programmes in how they approach curricular development. The results, however, are not allowing for drawing causal conclusion. For instance, the lack of focus on sustainability in eastern European engineering education might be explained by the fact that they implemented these issues a long time ago into their programmes or because it is yet to get attention. In order to analyse the data further, the number of respondents from different regions and programmes should increase.

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